

POS-Tagging Historical Corpora: The Case of Early New High German

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Abstract

A key problem in automatic annotation of historical corpora is inconsistent spelling. Because the spelling of some word forms can differ between texts, a language model trained on already annotated treebanks may fail to recognize known word forms due to differences in spelling. In the present work, we explore the feasibility of an unsupervised method for spelling-adjustment for the purpose of improved part of speech (POS) tagging. To this end, we present a method for spelling normalization based on weighted edit distances, which exploits within-text spelling variation. We then evaluate the improvement in tagging accuracy resulting from between-texts spelling normalization in two tagging experiments on several Early New High German (ENHG) texts.

1 Introduction

A key problem in automatic annotation of historical corpora is inconsistent spelling [1, 7, 8, 4]. The spelling of words varies across texts, and sometimes even within a text. For example, the preposition *über* ('over') can be spelled as *über* or as *vber*. The word *frauen* ('women') may also occur in the form *fraun* or as *frauwn*. A large part of the spelling inconsistency can be attributed to the lack of clear orthographic conventions at the time, as well as to the fact that some texts were incrementally written over a period of time, thus increasing the chance of inconsistent spelling even by a single author. This ubiquitous variation in spelling may complicate (semi-) automatic annotation of historical texts, because some word forms may appear to be unknown to a language model trained on already annotated treebanks, because their spelling differs between texts.

In the present work, we explore the feasibility of an unsupervised method for spelling-adjustment for the purpose of improved part of speech (POS) tagging and semi-automatic syntactic annotation. To this end, we conducted a series of POS tagging experiments on four syntactically annotated Early New High German

(*ENHG* henceforth) texts from the “Referenzkorpus Frühneuhochdeutsch”,¹ and compared the accuracy of POS tagging models based on original texts and texts with normalized spelling.

2 Methods for recognition of spelling variation

Several approaches were developed in the recent years to recognize a spelling variant as an instance of a standard spelling. One is to use dictionaries if a language period exhibits normative spelling rules. In the case of *ENHG* two big digital sources are available: the “Deutsches Rechtswörterbuch”² and “Deutsches Wörterbuch” by Jacob und Wilhelm Grimm.³ Pilz [8] searched for 100 word forms from three *ENHG* texts in both dictionaries and found that over 66% of the tested spelling variants were not present in the dictionaries. Thus, searching for various spellings in dictionaries does not appear to be promising approach by itself.

Another approach is the application of manually specified rules transforming one string into another. This is quite time-consuming and may not be reliable, because the created rules may not generalize to unobserved text. Therefore, some approaches combine manually and automatically generated rules. Human post-editors then decide whether two suggestions are related spelling variants. Such approaches can reach fairly high accuracy rates as Ernst-Gerlach and Fuhr show [4]. Bollmann et al. [1] developed a normalization tool for *ENHG* spelling variants. They combine manually developed rewrite guidelines, word lists, Levenshtein’s edit distance, modern lexicon lookup and human evaluation to optimize rewrite rules and to improve normalization suggestions. Normalized word forms then can be compared with modern New High German (*NHG* henceforth) word forms in order to connect *ENHG* and *NHG* lemmatization.

Another approach is to use text corpora instead of dictionaries or rules, particularly if the usage of dictionaries or rules is not possible or is not promising enough. Pilz [8] uses *ENHG* texts and combines edit distances with machine learning techniques to produce a metric (*FlexMetrik*) estimating whether two word forms are spelling variants of one another.

Jurish [7] tested several approaches for recognizing spelling variants on *NHG* texts from the *Deutsches Textarchiv*⁴ published between 1780 and 1880. In one of the approaches, Jurish uses Hidden Markov Models to identify the most likely lexical candidate with respect to the sentential context. This procedure allows token-wise disambiguation instead of single type-wise identification and reaches a precision of over 99%, because even difficult word forms which belong to different lexical categories can be recognized (such as, for example, the *ENHG* word form ‘*im*’, which can function as preposition ‘*in*’, or as the pronoun ‘*him*’). As Jurish

¹<http://www.ruhr-uni-bochum.de/wegera/ref/>

²<http://www.rzuser.uni-heidelberg.de/cd2/drw/>

³<http://dwb.uni-trier.de>

⁴<http://www.deutschestextarchiv.de>

Table 1: Overview of text statistics.

	Text	Year	Tokens	Types	Types/Tokens
1	BdN	1350-1375	21,104	3,463	0.16
2	Denkwürdigkeiten	1451	16,614	2,200	0.13
3	Pfaffe	1471	19,379	3,299	0.17
4	BvK	1465	25,213	3,360	0.13

points out, the performance of Hidden Markov Models on sparse data and on texts with rather heterogeneous spelling, such as ENHG texts, remains to be tested.

3 Corpora

In order to evaluate the effect of spelling normalization across texts on POS-tagging, we used four syntactically annotated Early New High German texts from the “*Referenzkorpus Frühneuhochdeutsch*”. The texts were written between 1350 and 1650, and belong to different language fields, i.e., to different epochs, regions and text genres.⁵ The transliterated texts were annotated with the semi-automatic annotation tool @nnotate [3]. We used a part of speech tag set for historical texts that allows detailed lexical categorization considering historical word order [5].⁶ Furthermore, the annotated texts contain syntactic and, in some cases, morphological information.

The four texts we used were “Das Buch der Natur” (*Book of nature*), “Denkwürdigkeiten” (*Reminiscences*), “Des pfaffen geschicht vnd histori vom Kalenberg” (*The history of the cleric of Kalenberg*) and “Das Buch aller verbotenen Künste” (*The book of all forbidden arts*). All texts were dated from the second half of the 14th until the second half of the 15th century. Table 1 provides an overview over the text statistics.

The first text in table 1 is the Bavarian text “Das Buch der Natur” (*Book of nature*, ‘BvK’ henceforth). It was written in the second half of the 14th century by Konrad Megenberg in Regensburg and is thus the earliest text in the corpus.

The second text, “Denkwürdigkeiten” (*Reminiscences*) is a travel diary written around 1451 by Helene Kottanerin, who was a handmaiden to Queen Elizabeth of Hungary and her daughter Elizabeth of Austria. In the diary, she documented a journey with the pregnant princess Elizabeth. The Upper German text exhibits various spelling variations, including instances of highly frequent words. A possible reason for that is that the text was written incrementally over the course of a long period of time and that the author was not a professional writer.

⁵The corpus development is covered by grant DE 677/7 of the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG).

⁶For example, our tag set differs from STTS [9] in having additional tags for adjectives to cover post-nominal modification and nominalized usage. Furthermore, our tag set marks discontinuous usage of prepositional adverbs, which is quite frequent in ENHG.

The third text, “Des pfaffen geschicht vnd histori vom Kalenberg” (*The history of the cleric of Kalenberg*; ‘*Pfaffe*’ henceforth) is a satirical story in verses written by Philipp Frankfurter during the second half of the 15th century. The first edition of the West Middle German text was published in Augsburg in 1471 and has less apparent spelling variation than ‘*Denkwürdigkeiten*’.

The fourth text, named “Das Buch aller verbotenen Künste. Des Aberglaubens und der Zauberei” (*Book of all forbidden arts, superstition and sorcery*, ‘*BvK*’ henceforth), was written by Johannes Hartlieb in the 1450s and concerns the forbidden magical arts like geomancy, pyromancy or aeromancy. Our edition of the Swabian text was published in Augsburg in 1465.

4 Examples of spelling variation in historical texts

A typical example of spelling alternations between texts involve allographs such as *zz* and *ss*, or *ch* and *ck*. Such alternations are exemplified in (1a) and (1b).

- (1) a. Wan ez geschicht oft daz darin velt von **ezzen** oder von **trinchen**
 Because it happens often that therein lacks of eat or of drink
 ‘Because it often happens that food and drinking is lacking therein’ (*BdN_301*)
- b. Dieselb kranckhait mag man mit kainem **essen** oder **trincken** [...]
 The-same illness might one with no eating or drink [...]
 erfüllen
 fulfill
 ‘One cannot heal that illness with either food or drinking’ (*BvK_795*)

Examples of intratextual frequent spelling variants in ‘*BdN*’ (text 1) involve alternations of *c* and *ch* in words such as *nihts*, *nichts*, *nichtz* (nothing) or *chlain*, *clain* (short).

In ‘*Denkwürdigkeiten*’, while the definite article *die* occurs 338 times, it occurs another 57 times in its alternative version *dy*. Furthermore, the adjective *edel* (*noble*) is also spelled as *edl* (62 and 20 occurrences, respectively). Another spelling variation we found with the subordinating conjunction *that*: It occurs 192 times as *daz* (2a) and only three times as *das* (2b). The spelling *das* is mainly used for pronouns and articles, while *daz* marks the usage as conjunction. The other texts, in contrast, exhibit consistent spellings of *that* either as *daz* (‘*BdN*’) or as *das* (‘*Pfaffe*’, ‘*BvK*’).

- (2) a. [die herren] waren fro **daz-KOUS**⁷ sich ir gnad gewilligt het
 [the gentlemen] were glad that-*KOUS* herself her Grace acquiesced has
 den von polan ze nemen.
 the one of Poland to take.
 ‘[the gentlemen] were glad that her Grace had acquiesced to take the one of Poland [in marriage].’ (*Denkwürdigkeiten_71*)

- b. jch solt mich wol gehabt / **das-KOUS** wer aus komen [..]
 I should me well being / that-KOUS we out come [..]
 'I should be confident / that we come out [..]' (Denkwürdigkeiten_141)

In 'Pfaffe', we found four spelling variants of the personal pronoun *sie* (singular, *she*) and *sie* (plural, *they*): *si* (plural: 1 occurrence), *sy* (singular: 19 times; plural: 25 times), *sie* (singular: 44 times; plural: 60 times), *sye* (singular: 17 times; plural: 56 times). Furthermore, we found nine different spelling variations on one of the dominant themes of the book: *tiüffel* (*devil*), five of which occur 15 times or more.

There is also some variation in the spelling of technical terms. Names of magical arts are typically formed with the morpheme *-mancia*, as in *geomancia* (*geomancy*). However, they also occur in the alternative spelling *mantia*. Furthermore, the lexemes *aeromantia* and *nigramantia* occur in alternative spellings with the prefixes *are-*, *aro-* and *nygra-*, respectively.

5 POS tagging accuracy in historical corpora

In order to evaluate whether spelling normalization can increase POS tagging accuracy, we used the TnT tagger [2] to tag each text using, in turn, each of the three remaining texts or the remaining texts as whole as the underlying language model. We did so in order to establish a base line to compare the tagging accuracy before and after spelling normalization.

Table 2 shows the results of the tagging experiments for each target text averaged over all language models used for tagging that text. It shows the percentage of unknown tokens, the percentage of correctly assigned tags, as well as the tagging accuracies for known as well as unknown types separately.

Table 2: Overview of the results of the POS-tagging experiments using unmodified corpora. Average percentages with standard deviations in parentheses. Text ids correspond to ids in table 1.

target text	training corpus	% correct	% unknown	% correct (known)	% correct (unknown)
1	2, 3, 4, 2&3&4	69 (5)	35 (6)	87 (1)	37 (6)
2	1, 3, 4, 1&3&4	76 (4)	27 (5)	87 (1)	46 (7)
3	1, 2, 4, 1&2&4	70 (5)	31 (6)	85 (2)	36 (6)
4	1, 2, 3, 1&2&3	75 (5)	28 (6)	86 (2)	48 (7)

Across texts, the overall tagging accuracy was 73%, with a significantly higher accuracy for known tokens (86%) and than for unknown tokens (42%). The relatively low accuracy for previously unseen types for text 1 (approximately 36%, as

⁷The part of speech tag 'KOUS' stands for subordinating conjunctions.

opposed to approximately 47% in the other two texts) is possibly caused by differences in syntactic patterns due to the fact that text 1 (*BdN*) is significantly older than the remaining texts. The lower accuracy for text 3 (*Pfaffe*), on the other hand, is likely caused by the verse structure of that text, which is not present in the remaining texts. Thus, because the unusual syntactic constructions in parts of the text were rarely present in the training data, the TnT tagger’s second-order Markov model cannot reliably use an unknown word’s POS-context to assign it to a POS category. This difference suggests that the text genre affects the tagging accuracy.

Not unexpectedly, the highest proportions of unknown word forms were found among open class words (adjectives, nouns, and verbs). Among these classes, the average proportion of unknown tokens was 51% (SD=19%). Adverbs had a somewhat lower unknown token rate of 26% (SD=10%). The lowest rates of unknowns were found among closed class words (articles, conjunctions, prepositions, pronouns) with an average of 11% (SD = 6). Closed class words were associated with an average accuracy of 76%. The latter is not unexpected, because these lexical categories contain only few words. However, the tagger does not perform well on unknown closed-class words: tagging correctness for unknown conjunctions was under 20%, with an average of 10% and only 2% on the text “Denkwürdigkeiten”.

6 Word similarity metric

In order to broaden the coverage of the language model, we normalized word spelling across texts using a metric of distance between word forms. We assumed that two word forms are spelling variants of a single lexeme and should be conflated when they occurred in the same environments (as assessed by a bigram model), and when they were sufficiently similar to each other in terms of spelling. We assessed word similarity by means of a weighted edit distance metric [6], which is an indicator of the number of character changes required to transform one word into the other.

For example, the unweighted edit distance between *cat* and *mat* is 1, because a ‘c’ needs to be substituted by an ‘m’ or vice versa to transform one word into the other. The edit distance between *rice* and *ice* is also 1, because an ‘r’ needs to be deleted or inserted. However, if we decided to penalize insertions and deletions twice as much as substitutions, the weighted edit distance between *rice* and *ice* would be 2. In a similar manner, different substitutions can be penalized differently. For example, the substitution ‘b’ → ‘z’ appears, *a priori*, less likely to produce an alternative spelling of the same lexeme than the substitution ‘b’ → ‘p’. We used a weighted edit distance to capture this fact.

More formally, we assumed that the word forms w_i and w_j were instances of the same lexeme when the inequality in equation 1 was satisfied. In this equation, $P_{bigram}(texts|w_i \leftrightarrow w_j)$ is the bigram probability of the texts *assuming* the conflation of w_i and w_j (i.e., assuming that w_i are instances of the same lexeme in different spelling), while $P_{bigram}(texts|w_i \not\leftrightarrow w_j)$ is the probability of the texts *not assuming*

a conflation of w_i and w_j (i.e., that w_j and w_i are distinct words). Furthermore, $P(w_i \leftrightarrow w_j)$ is the prior probability of w_i corresponding to w_j , as assessed by means of a weighted edit distance.

In other words, we conflated two word forms when the increase in the probability of the two texts according to a bigram model of both texts outweighed the prior probability of the change in word form according to equations 2 and 3.

$$P_{\text{bigram}}(\text{texts}|w_i \leftrightarrow w_j) \cdot P(w_i \leftrightarrow w_j) > P_{\text{bigram}}(\text{texts}|w_i \not\leftrightarrow w_j) \quad (1)$$

The prior probability of word w_i corresponding to w_j was computed according to equation 2 as the product of the prior probabilities of all edit operations required to transform w_i to w_j .

$$P(w_i \leftrightarrow w_j) = \prod_{\forall e \in \text{edits}(w_i \rightarrow w_j)} P(e) \quad (2)$$

In setting prior probabilities of single edit operations we exploited the within-text spelling variation in the training corpus. First, we identified all pairs of word forms in the training corpus which can be transferred into each other with exactly one edit operation (such as *cat* and *mat*). Next, for every pair of such words w_k and w_m , we computed the probability p_{km} that w_k and w_m each occur with the POS tags assigned to them in the training corpus, assuming that they are spelling variants of the same word, and therefore theoretically occur with the same POS tags equally often. This means that if w_k and w_m mostly occurred with the same POS-tags, p_{km} was large, while it was relatively small if the two words were rarely assigned the same POS tags.

We set the prior probability for every edit operation e to the geometric mean of all p_{km} according to equation 3, where w_k can be transferred into w_m with the edit operation e and where n is the number of such word form pairs. $P(e)$ was set to 1 for all edits operations for which no minimal pairs existed.⁸ Set up in this way, the prior probability captures the negative evidence against some edit operations which is present in the corpus, while it does not penalize edit operations for which no minimal pair was observed.

$$P(e) = \sqrt[n]{\prod_{\forall w_k, w_m: w_k \xrightarrow{e} w_m} p_{km}} \quad (3)$$

7 Tagging normalized texts

In order to test our metric, we conflated all sufficiently similar words in all pairs of training and test sets, if those words did not differ by more than three characters and if at least one of them occurred in the test set but not in the training set. The latter condition was used because conflating two words which are not in the test set

⁸The prior probabilities do not sum to 1, because they concern independent events.

cannot possibly result in higher POS tagging accuracy. In the next step, we used the TnT tagger [2] to tag the normalized texts.

The differences in accuracy between the results in table 2 and the tagging experiments are presented in table 3. It shows that texts 1 and 2 appear to substantially benefit from spelling normalization, with an average improvement of 2.2 percentage points in accuracy, while the tagging accuracy on texts 3 and 4 seems largely unchanged. This difference appears largely due to the fact that only 0.5% of all tokens in texts 3 and 4 were affected by the conflation (the percentage of unknown tokens decreased by approximately 0.6 percentage points), *vis-à-vis* the approximately 2% affected in texts 1 and 2.

Table 3: Differences between the results of the POS tagging experiments using normalized and original spelling.

test corpus	training corpora	% correct	% unknown	% correct (known)	% correct (unknown)
1	2, 3, 4, 2&3&4	1.4 (1.7)	-2.0 (2.1)	-0.3 (0.3)	1.7 (2.3)
2	1, 3, 4, 1&3&4	1.6 (0.8)	-1.9 (1.1)	0.1 (0.1)	2.9 (1.5)
3	1, 2, 4, 1&2&4	0.2 (0.2)	-0.4 (0.2)	-0.1 (0.1)	0.1 (0.1)
4	1, 2, 3, 1&2&3	-0.2 (0.3)	-0.7 (0.4)	-0.2 (0.4)	-1.2 (1.7)

Across the board, the largest contribution to the reduction in the number of unknown tokens for text 2 was due to the conflation of four pairs of highly frequent word forms, with the major share being due to the conflation of the word forms *das* (198 occurrences in text 2) and *daz* (228 occurrences in text 2). While *das* appeared with various POS tags (e.g., demonstrative pronoun, definite article, and conjunction) and was present in all texts, *daz* appeared almost exclusively as a conjunction in text 2. The situation in text 1 was similar: the conflation of *daz* and *das* appeared to play a significant role, but also that of other closed-class tokens, such as *darumb* and *darvmb* (*therefore*), or *uon* and *von* (*from*). Better coverage of highly frequent function types also explains the increase in accuracy for unknown word forms — because more highly frequent word forms are known, and are therefore recognized more reliably, the tagger can use that context to guess the POS of more unknown tokens in their surroundings.

In summary, our results suggest that spelling normalization may improve the quality of (semi-)automatic annotation, especially if the target text exhibits a high degree of spelling variability, or if there are systematic differences in spelling between texts.

8 Discussion

In the present paper, we investigated the idea that normalizing spelling across historical texts may improve the coverage of language models in automatic annotation. We presented an unsupervised method for identifying alternative spellings of the

same lexeme in historical texts. We tested its performance on four Early New High German texts.

Although the performance was mixed, our results suggest that especially texts with large spelling variation such as our texts 1 and 2 (*'BdN'* and *'Reminiscences'*) may benefit from such normalization. This is especially so, when the spelling of highly frequent functional lexemes varies between texts, because the identification of alternative spelling variants can have a positive effect not only on the correct assignment of POS categories to known, but also to previously unseen, unknown tokens.

A clear limitation of our approach is that it considers edit operations only at the level of a single character and is therefore unable to capture higher-level generalizations, for example, the alternation of character sequences *'ie'* by *'y'* (such as in *die*, a definite article, and its alternative spelling *'dy'*), as the substitution of one character (*'i'* or *'e'*) by *'y'*, and the deletion of the other character. A consequence of that is the inability to represent the fact that the deletion of *'i'* or *'e'* may produce an entirely different word, and not a spelling variant, in other contexts.

We suspect that more sophisticated methods, which are able to capture alternations between character sequences, such as variations on [1, 7], may lead to significant performance increases over our metric.

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